

Lia Metreveli

*full professor, PhD in educational sciences,
faculty of Engineering economics,
media technologies and Social Sciences,
Georgian Technical University
Tbilisi, Georgia*

Tinatin Tcharkhalashvili

*assistant professor, PhD in social sciences
faculty of Engineering economics,
media technologies and Social Sciences,
Georgian Technical University
Tbilisi, Georgia*

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' RESEARCH SKILLS, CULTURAL AND COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE USING MUSEUM EXHIBITS

Abstract. Museums are the best places for discovery and learning, they are the guardians of world heritage, creating a continuous link between the past and the future. With the help of museums, students can compare information, analyse and evaluate the processes taking place in the world today, discuss the geographical features of global processes and events, and socio-cultural aspects of globalization. In modern life, this issue is particularly relevant. This was also helped by the fact that the educational potential of museums was re-evaluated, which in turn showed us a greater need for learning through museums. At all levels of pedagogy, the idea that the role of museums in the process of learning and acquiring 21st century skills is immeasurably greater is discussed. The involvement of museums of different profiles is equally important in the case of museum education. For example: lore museums, museum reserves, university museums, art museums. Each of them can play their role in effectively conducting educational activities.

The article discusses the promotion of the integrated teaching of the subject by conducting a museum-lesson for which it uses the rich funds at its disposal.

Among them, by promoting the integrated teaching of basic fundamental sciences (natural, public, technical), museum education awakens creative abilities in students, pushes them combine theoretical and practical knowledge, activate analytical thinking, manage ideas, make decisions about productive activities, it helps to create a unified view of the world. Its use in the educational process is necessary and very important.

Key words: Museum education, Educational process, Museum exhibit, Student, School.

Introduction

At the beginning of the twenty-first century, serious changes took place in museums; they took on a new function and became the focus of the educational space. It can be safely said that museums are one of the main stimulators of the development of today's society.

The visit of students at all levels of the general educational institution not only consolidates the knowledge received in the classroom, but also forms a special vision of the world in the adolescents. The curiosity and interest aroused in the adolescent while in the museum plays a big role in his personal development and socialization.

The museum has the magical power to seriously contribute to the educational process of the school in many directions. One important factor is the visual communication of the exhibits and artefacts that adults see in the museum. When viewing the relevant exhibition, history, physics, geography, chemistry, astronomy, mathematics, art become more interesting, understandable and diverse for them.

For educators interested in conducting integrated lessons, the museum space offers an environment that will enrich their lessons informatively at all levels of teaching. At the modern stage of teaching, in a successful teaching process, it is important to raise the problematic issues in the school, to analyse the challenges, to draw up a charity plan and to take concrete steps. The main thing is for the teacher to apply a variety of strategies, following the national curriculum. In this process, teacher should take into account that different types of students study in the class, which means that they have different abilities to learn and learn new material. The best solution is a differentiated approach.

There are basically three types of learning: visual, auditory and kinaesthetic. Practical experience shows that the majority of students have the ability to perceive visually. Obviously, such students need to be taught by seeing the material to be studied, so that the subject becomes more interesting and understandable. As for the students who have auditory absorption skills, they prefer to learn by sitting, listening and reading aloud. Kinaesthetic learners need to move and hold or touch learning materials. It can be safely said that the best environment for all three types of students is the museum space. Therefore, museum teaching can be considered as a pedagogical technology, the role and importance of which is becoming more necessary and important.

Main part

Museum excursions

It should be noted that the excursion to the museum as a form of communication between the visitor and the exhibit was formed in ancient Babylon, Egypt and ancient Greece. The term "excursion" (Lat. Excursio – walk, trip) was coined at the turn of the 18th-19th centuries. Museum education experts point out that since the 19th century, excursions have been part of the educational process of many schools.

This process remains a democratic form of educational activity, the purpose of which is to help the school community, and not only, to gain new knowledge and experience.

In modern museology, three types of museum excursion are distinguished, namely: overview excursion, educational excursion and cognitive excursion.

The purpose of the overview tour is to create a general idea for the visitors about the museum and its exhibits. As for the educational excursion, in contrast to the overview excursion, the purpose of the educational excursion is to perceive and understand specific issues in depth. On this type of excursion, it is possible to carry out such educational activities, which will be prepared based on the educational program of the school and will allow students to deepen the

knowledge received at school in an informal environment, or even to learn about the subjects to be studied at school during an educational excursion in the museum.

The third form of a museum excursion is a cognitive excursion, the purpose of which is to develop the skills of the participant to fully perceive the museum exhibit. Along with the educational excursion, the cognitive excursion is also a type of museum activity that has a pedagogical direction and is considered as a preparatory stage for a complete understanding of the issue. It should be noted that the cognitive excursion was first conducted by A. Lichtwark (Alfred Lichtwark, 1852). Alfred Lichtwark considered the museum to be the main centre of education along with the school. The scientist believed that the excursion was the main form of educational activity, and he had his own methodological principles for the preparation of the excursion.

This type of excursion encourages creative imagination. Lichtwark thought that his main duty was to work with children in the form of excursions, and he considered the school and the museum to be the main place of education. A. Lichtwark wrote: "We develop aesthetic skills, the ability to convey one's own opinion and impressions verbally, which is very important in the process of personality formation, and it is the development of these skills that the national curriculum of Georgia aims at".

Conclusion

The formation of students' research skills, general cultural and communicative competences, as well as the effective management of the educational process using museum exhibits, will be successful, while there will be a correct strategy and mandatory museum lessons will be implemented, both in the museum space and outside the museum (in schools), because it is possible for museums to have a short period of time. Schools are asking for museum exhibits from their own collections. These exhibits are used by teachers as real samples of the material they provide to students. Exhibits should be handed over in special boxes with instructions for teachers. The service of retrieving exhibits is extremely useful, because it is possible that the "things" that were useless in the warehouse can be used for educational purposes, both for teachers and students. They encourage the representatives of the school community to visit the museum and view the exhibits of the museum collection.

Recommendations

➤ Live lessons conducted in both school and museum by museum staff or teachers will be more interesting and understandable through film or slide shows and conversations, because students like when someone else talks to them besides the teacher, in addition, the use of photo materials (photo slides) develops children's imagination and helps to express feelings and impressions evoked by museum exhibits.

➤ It is important to organize extraordinary events, which are the most effective means of providing educational services. Events can take different forms. For example: wearing clothes typical of a specific historical period and giving children a means to develop this theme based on their own views.

➤ Museums should produce different types of children's publications. Materials presented in written form allow children and parents to take part of the museum with them. The first step is to carefully prepare the layout and design of the book. When buying a book, children pay attention to colours and pictures. Parents want to buy a book that is well written and easy to understand. Museum staff should conduct research based on museum lessons, consider the positive aspects of museum pedagogy, write a book, and include an illustration.

➤ Teaching methods should be problem-based learning, mini-researches, active learning-teaching methods: imitative (imitation of museum exposition projection, virtual/imaginary excursions, etc.) as well as non-imitation (real projection, museum games). Use of analytical-evaluative methods, group discussions, excursions, dramatization, simulation and role-playing games and presentations.

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